

Description datafile: 'Water level and vegetation type control carbon fluxes in a newly-constructed soft-sediment wetland'

This datafile is part of a study that shows how the emissions of greenhouse gasses relate to organic matter, water table and plant coverage and how soil is affected by the presence of vegetation and specific wetland species. The measurements were conducted on a newly-constructed archipelago for nature named Marker Wadden in the Netherlands in the end of June of 2020.

This file includes (see codebook below for details) data obtained with a field measurements on Marker Wadden (the Netherlands, datafile "Tak et al field data"). The datafile contains data related to vegetation, greenhouse gas fluxes and soil chemistry. Not all data were used in the manuscript (e.g. soil type, bulk density, and the concentrations of PO₄, NO₃, NH₄, Cl, Al, Ca, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, S, Si and Zn), but were provided as additional information to interested researchers. In addition, we have provided all calculated respiration rates of the MicroResp analysis (datafile "Tak et al MicroResp data").

Note that every location had two plots, one vegetated and one unvegetated.

Codebook

Data of the field measurements and lab analyses

Name	Description
Date	Date of measurement
Plot	Plot name
Location	The location of paired vegetated and bare soil plots
Category	<i>Category</i> of the presence or absence of vegetation
Soil_type	<i>Category</i> of the soil type
Water_level	<i>Measurement</i> of the ground water level (-) or water table on ground level (in cm)
Species_name	<i>Category</i> of the species present in every (vegetated) plot
Dominant_species	<i>Category</i> of the dominant species at every location
Cover.perc	<i>Measurement</i> of the cover of the dominant species (percentage)
Max_height	<i>Measurement</i> of maximum height of the dominant species (cm)
CH4_flux_light	<i>Measurement</i> of CH ₄ flux in light conditions (mg m ⁻² d ⁻¹)

CO2_flux_light	<i>Measurement of CO₂ flux in light conditions (mg m⁻² d⁻¹)</i>
CH4_flux_dark	<i>Measurement of CH₄ flux in dark conditions (mg m⁻² d⁻¹)</i>
CO2_flux_dark	<i>Measurement of CO₂ flux in dark conditions (mg m⁻² d⁻¹)</i>
CH4_flux_mean	<i>Calculated average of the CH₄ flux in light and dark conditions (mg m⁻² d⁻¹)</i>
effect_CH4_light	<i>Calculated difference between the CH₄ flux (light) in absence or presence of vegetation.</i>
effect_CO2_light	<i>Calculated difference between the CO₂ flux (light) in absence or presence of vegetation.</i>
effect_CH4_dark	<i>Calculated difference between the CH₄ flux (dark) in absence or presence of vegetation.</i>
effect_CO2_dark	<i>Calculated difference between the C O₂ flux (dark) in absence or presence of vegetation.</i>
effect_CH4_mean	<i>Calculated average of the difference in CH₄ flux (light and dark conditions) in absence or presence of vegetation.</i>
Water.content.g	<i>Measurement of the water content of the soil (gram)</i>
Bulk.density.kgdwl	<i>Measurement of the bulk density of the soil (kg dw liter⁻¹)</i>
OM.percentage	<i>Measurement of organic material of the soil (%)</i>
PO4	<i>Measurement of Concentration PO₄³⁻ in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
NO3	<i>Measurement of Concentration NO₃⁺ in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
NH4	<i>Measurement of Concentration NH₄⁻ in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Cl	<i>Measurement of Concentration Cl in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Al	<i>Measurement of Concentration Al in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Ca	<i>Measurement of Concentration Ca in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Fe	<i>Measurement of Concentration Fe in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
K	<i>Measurement of Concentration K in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹) – ICP</i>
Mg	<i>Measurement of Concentration Mg in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Mn	<i>Measurement of Concentration Mn in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Na	<i>Measurement of Concentration Na in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹) – ICP</i>
P	<i>Measurement of Concentration P in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
S	<i>Measurement of Concentration S in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Si	<i>Measurement of Concentration Si in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>
Zn	<i>Measurement of Concentration Zn in the soil samples (μmol L⁻¹)</i>

Data of the MicroResp analysis

Name	Description
Plot	Plot name
Category	<i>Category</i> of the presence or absence of vegetation
Substrate	<i>Category</i> of the carbon substrate added
Prod_rate	<i>Calculated</i> CO ₂ production rate ($\mu\text{g CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ soil h}^{-1}$)
Dominant_species	<i>Category</i> of the corresponding dominant species

Information on the study sites and sampling methodology:

Study site

Our study site was located in Lake Markermeer in the Netherlands, which was formerly part of the inland sea Zuiderzee, but was closed off from the Wadden Sea by the construction of two dykes (Afsluitdijk and Houtribdijk) (**Fig. 1A**, for more information, see van Leeuwen et al. (2021)). This converted the system from a marine estuary to a shallow and turbid freshwater lake. Ecological values including biodiversity have gradually declined over time (Cremer et al., 2009; Noordhuis, 2014; van Leeuwen et al., 2021). To improve the ecological state of Lake Markermeer, the Dutch Society for Nature Conservation ('Natuurmonumenten') started a forward-looking restoration project. A 700-ha human-made archipelago named Marker Wadden was constructed between 2016 and 2020 to create shelter and gradual land-to-water transitions (**Fig. 1B**, 52°35'30"N 5°22'43"E). The wetlands were created by first constructing ring dikes of sand, which were filled up with Holocene marine clay and silt that was pumped from the bottom of the lake up to a depth of -20 m (Saaltink et al., 2016; van Leeuwen et al., 2021). The elevation of Marker Wadden lies between c. 0 (marsh) and 1.5 m (sandy walking paths) N.A.P (c. mean sea level). Soil formation started after construction and typically entailed enrichment with organic matter and, depending on vegetation type, a thick organic layer. The water level of Lake Markermeer is managed and protected from future sea level rise by the Afsluitdijk (i.e., a dam between the sea – both Wadden and indirectly the North Sea and the freshwater lakes). For more information regarding the aims and ecological concept of Marker Wadden, the effects of herbivory, shelter, or primary production in the aquatic system, see van Leeuwen et al. (2021); Saaltink et al. (2019), Jin et al. (2022) and Temmink et al. (2022b).

Study design

To study the effect of vegetation type (vegetation for brevity) on GHG fluxes, 32 vegetated and 32 bare plots of approximately 1 m² were sampled. All vegetated plots consisted of one ($n = 19$ plots) or two ($n = 2$ plots) dominant plant species. The dominant species were *Cotula coronopifolia*, *Epilobium hirsutum*, *Phragmites australis*, *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Rumex maritimus*, and *Typha latifolia* ($n = 7$ for *R. maritimus* and $n = 5$ for the other species). At 0.5-1 m distance from a vegetated plot, a bare plot with visually similar abiotic conditions was selected. To minimize differences in soil type and time since construction (three years), all plots were selected on the same island (**Fig. 1C**) and were sampled between July 21st and 23rd in 2020. The days (09.00-17.00h) were comparable in temperature (average temperature day 1: 18.5°C, day 2: 17.7°C, day 3: 21.2°C), and precipitation (0.0 mm on all days). All measurements were conducted

in full sunlight with a clear sky (day 1: 09.00-17.00h, day 2: 08.00-15.00h, day 3: 09.00-12.00h & 14.00-17.00h).

Figure 1. The Marker Wadden archipelago. (A) its location (red box) in the Netherlands (inset, blue) with the two major dykes shaping the current system (Afsluitdijk and Houtribdijk); (B) the newly constructed archipelago Marker Wadden with soft-sediment wetlands (green); (C) Locations of the sampled plots. Maps were created with Natural Earth (A) and with OpenStreetMap (B-C).

Greenhouse gas measurements

We measured CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes in all plots using closed transparent and opaque PVC chambers (diameter 50 cm, height depending on the vegetation: 25-200 cm, fitted with a circulating fan), which were placed on the sediment as such that an airtight seal was established. Chamber height could be adjusted by opaque open top rings where the closed top chambers could sit on. All connections were airtight. The chamber was connected to a LI-7810 Trace Gas Analyzer (LI-COR Biosciences GmbH, Bad Homburg, Germany) with TPE-U(PU) tubes (4 cm inner diameter) via two gas-tight ports in a closed loop. For

inundated plots, a floating chamber (30 cm diameter, height 17 cm) was used. Measurements lasted for c. 180s and included only diffusive fluxes (i.e., no ebullition) (Oliveira Junior et al., 2019). Gas fluxes in each plot were first measured with the transparent chamber to determine Net ecosystem CO₂ exchange (NEE) and then with an opaque chamber to calculate ecosystem respiration (R_{eco}). Light and dark measurements of CH₄ fluxes were averaged since they did not differ significantly. In the rare case of an abrupt increase in gas concentration, indicating ebullition, we removed the chamber, vented and replaced it (van Bergen et al., 2019). The differences in CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes between the vegetated plots and the corresponding bare plots were used to calculate the effect of the vegetation on the fluxes.

Vegetation, soil, and water table measurements

We determined total coverage of vegetation (%), species, cover per species (%), and maximum species height (cm) in each vegetated plot. After GHG measurements, we collected a soil sample in all plots from the top 10 cm, to assess organic matter content and soil microbial activity. Samples were stored in the dark at 4 °C until further analysis. To measure the groundwater level, we dug a 10-40 cm hole and let the water table stabilize for 30 min, after which we measured the water level relative to the soil surface with a ruler. In case the soil was inundated, we measured the depth from the sediment to the water surface.

Chemical analyses and ecophysiological profiling of the microbial community

Wet bulk density was determined by filling aluminum cups with soil and dividing the soil weight by the volume of the cups (38.8 ml). To determine water content and organic matter content of the soil, subsamples were first dried at 70°C to constant weight, after which the dried samples were ignited at 450°C for six hours, and remeasured afterward. The soil microbial activity and physiological soil profile were determined with MicroResp™ following (Campbell et al., 2003; Renault et al., 2013). First, all soils were acclimated to room temperature for 3-5 days. We ascertained that the water content of the soils (dry-weight/fresh-weight ratio) fell within the 30%-60% moisture range, following prior analysis (see above). To remove stones and large pieces of organic matter, all samples were sieved with a 2 mm sieve, after which deep-well plates were filled with approximately 400 µL soil per well. To assess the physiological profile of the soil, either demineralized water or 30 mg substrate per gram of soil water with different complexities was added. We added, in increasing order of complexity, fructose, glucose, and trehalose, and as a control demineralized water ($n = 4$ replicates per combination of soil and substrate) (Creamer et al., 2016). The amount of added substrate was standardized to 30 mg per gram of soil water. After substrate addition, colorimetric gel detection plates were filled with a combination of agar and a

cresol red indicator solution (cresol red (18.5 mg l^{-1}), potassium chloride (17 g l^{-1}), and sodium bicarbonate (0.315 g l^{-1}). The plates were stored in a dark desiccator for at least two days before the addition of soils and substrates, with self-indicating soda lime that absorbs carbon dioxide (CO_2) from the air and changes color as it becomes saturated, and a beaker of water to prevent the agar from drying out.

Soil was added to the deep-well plates the day before the actual incubation and stored at room temperature with an airtight seal to avoid evaporation of soil moisture. At the start of the incubation ($t = 0$), detection plates were read with a Spark® Multimode Microplate Reader (TECAN, Switzerland) at 570 nm. Only plates with less than a 5% Coefficient of Variance (%CoV) between the wells were used for analyses. Then, the carbon substrate solutions were added to the soil in the deep-well plates using a syringe. Immediately, the filled deep-well and detection plates were placed on top of each other and sealed airtight using a MicroResp™ rubber seal and clamp. After incubating the plates at 25°C for 6 hours, the detection plates were measured again with the Microplate Reader. The CO_2 respiration rates ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) were calculated using the difference in light absorption between the two measurements (Campbell et al., 2003; Creamer et al., 2016; Renault et al., 2013).

Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses were performed with RStudio version 4.0.3. Prior to analyses, variables CH_4 fluxes, plant cover percentage, soil OM content, and CO_2 production rate were log-transformed and R_{eco} and CO_2 production rates (MicroResp™) were square-root transformed to meet model assumptions (normality of model residuals and variance homogeneity, visually assessed using residual plots). To assess the effect of vegetation presence, we performed paired samples t-tests for CH_4 fluxes, R_{eco} , OM content, and CO_2 production rate and a Wilcoxon signed rank test for NEE. To test the effect of environmental variables, data from bare plots and vegetated plots were separated. Then, linear models were created with CH_4 fluxes, NEE, or R_{eco} as a dependent variable, and water table, OM content, and their interaction as independent variables. For vegetated plots, dominant plant species and plant cover percentage were added as additional independent variables. CO_2 production rates (i.e., MicroResp analyses) were compared in a linear model using only substrate for bare soils, and adding dominant plant species and their interaction with vegetated soils, as independent variables. Optimal models were chosen using backward selection based on lowest AIC value. Pair-wise differences between dominant plant species were tested using Tukey post-hoc tests if the main effect was significant. Values are reported as mean \pm standard error and differences were deemed significant at $p < 0.05$.

Additional information:

Additional information regarding the methods, references or results of this dataset can be found in:

Daniël B.Y. Tak, Renske J.E. Vroom, Robin Lexmond, Leon P.M. Lamers, Bjorn J.M. Robroek, Ralph J.M. Temmink. In press. Water level and vegetation type control carbon fluxes in a newly-constructed soft-sediment wetland. *Wetlands Ecology and Management*.